

Meta-modeling and Statistical Assurance for Virtual Bioequivalence Assessments Using PBPK Models

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Abstract

Introduction: We present applications of statistical assurance (also called integrated power, IP) calculations to virtual bioequivalence (VBE) assessment using a PBPK model of long-acting paliperidone palmitate injectable suspensions. We extend those calculations to safe-space analysis and compare them to Bayesian posterior estimates of the probability of bioequivalence for a test product.

Methods: To overcome a computation time barrier, we developed a meta-model of parallel clinical BE trials performed by a PBPK model we previously published. After fitting the meta-model to PBPK simulation results, it can then be used to simulate very efficiently trials to which the two-one-sided t test can be applied. This enables Monte Carlo calculations of IP of VBE, which would be otherwise unfeasible. IP estimates were mapped onto the CQA parameter space to define integrated safe-space. The meta-model also efficiently computes posterior Bayesian estimates of test over formulation mean differences, which can be used for decision-making on BE.

Results: IP of LAI-PBPK model-generated VBE trials submitted to TOST testing is lower than standard power because it accounts for uncertainty in CQA values, which is essential in VBE assessment. Power-integrated safe-space is also reduced to an extent depending on CQA values uncertainty. IPs for very large trials are equal to the Bayesian estimates of the probability of bioequivalence.

Discussion: IP calculations bridge standard power calculations and a Bayesian decision rule equivalent to TOST in the limit of large trials. Since trial size is an arbitrary nuisance

parameter in VBE assessment, this offers a principled way to decide on virtual bioequivalence. Meta-modeling is an essential enabling ingredient in this innovative framework and its workflow. Model validation and a precise quantification of its uncertainty is essential in this framework.

Introduction

We have recently demonstrated a frequentist virtual bioequivalence (VBE) assessment workflow for physiologically-based biopharmaceutical models (PBBM) coupled to PBPK models [1–3]. Its main components were model validation, virtual trial simulations, TOST tests on the simulated trials, and assessment of TOST statistical power, type 1 error and formulation safe-space calculations. Whilst this workflow enabled the precise calculation of these components, it assumed exactly known test to reference differences and was unable to account for the impact of fundamental uncertainties in those differences. Several questions were subsequently left open to further investigations, the main being power calculations integrated over critical quality attributes' uncertainty – also known as statistical assurance [4–7] – and Bayesian VBE assessment [1]. IP offers more robust estimates of sample sizes needed for prescribed probabilities of declaring bioequivalence (BE), because its calculations account for the uncertainty that is always present on the value of the test and reference formulation critical quality attributes (CQA). Bayesian calculations were shown to bypass the need for virtual trial simulations, focusing only on the total information available, without degrading it with sub-sampling [1]. The major barrier to studying those questions for PBBMs is essentially computation speed. For example, power calculations for a single test product using parallel VBE trials of reasonable sizes (leading to at least 80% power) currently take about 10 hours on a 26-core virtual machine when using the Simcyp® Simulator LAI suspension model parameterized for paliperidone palmitate (PP) 3-month suspensions like INVEGA TRINZA®. Due to their incorporation of CQA values originating from a probability distribution as opposed to a single point estimate, IP calculations would take many days at a prohibitive cost, and Bayesian calculations would be even less feasible.

The use of meta-models, which can circumvent the need to run VBE trial simulations, can make these heavier calculations more feasible. When computing the type 1 error of VBE trials for PP LAI suspensions [3], we had to determine the absolute limits of the true bioequivalence region using numerical inversion of the PBPK model. This took a few hundred hours of calculations, and in addition to the boundaries of the true bioequivalence region, it also gave

us all the results needed to build a meta-model emulating our complex LAI-PBPK model. This meta-model is able to simulate parallel VBE trials for PP formulations much faster than the LAI-PBPK model itself. A meta-model is a local statistical approximation of a much more complex, often mechanistic, model [8–16]. The original model is first run to generate predictions for a given set of input values; in a second step, the relationship between original inputs and simulated values (taken as “observed data”) is statistically modeled using a regression model (or a neural network, or anything convenient and fast to compute). That model must mimic adequately the original one and should not be used for extrapolation outside the bounds of the input values of the original model. The meta-model can replace the original model to make predictions of the same nature. We know through our previous power calculations that for PP LAI suspensions, C_{max} yields the most stringent criterion for bioequivalence, so in the following study we focus, without loss of generality, on finding the safe-space limits for C_{max} BE. We therefore developed a meta-model able to predict the C_{max} geometric mean ratios (GMRs) and population variances of parallel BE trials, when provided a given trial size and drug mean particle size (the CQA of the original PBBM model). C_{max} GMRs and population variances are sufficient statistics to compute IP, uncertainty-integrated safe-space, and Bayesian posterior distribution estimates. We show how to perform those calculations in the case of PP LAI suspension formulations, study their results, and discuss their applicability.

Background on integrated power (statistical assurance)

Power calculations are usually made for fixed differences between test and reference formulations, even when planning future trials on formulations with uncertain relative effects. However, in reality we do not know exactly the size of those differences, except, maybe, if we compare only reference to reference. When planning a trial without the help of a pharmacokinetic model, it may be enough to assume a difference (a shift) in concentration vs. time profiles (equivalently, in C_{max} or AUC GMRs) between the test arm and the reference arm, and then run simulations of the TOST procedure to evaluate the probability of declaring bioequivalence. When using a model to link concentration profiles to formulation characteristics (CQAs), drug properties, and physiological variables, the differences of interest lay in the CQA values themselves, and model simulations should be used to translate those into GMRs. In either case, CQA differences between test and reference are estimated or measured in various ways, but with a fundamental uncertainty that power calculations should

consider. The solution to that is to define a probability distribution for GMRs (in the model-free case) and then integrate (or equivalently, form a weighted average) power estimates over that distribution using exact or Monte Carlo methods. This provides IP estimates, also called statistical assurances [4,5,7]. If a model is used, a probability distribution should be defined for CQA differences. Monte Carlo simulations of the model can then be used to obtain samples from the resulting distribution of test to reference GMRs, and for each sampled GMR a power estimate should be obtained with those power estimates being averaged to obtain an IP value.

There is an essential difference between the results of standard power and IP analyses. Both depend on trial size and on the CQA difference (*in fine*, test to reference GMR), but standard power should always approach and ultimately reach 100% as trial size increases, so long as the fundamental CQA difference does not imply non-bioequivalence. This is because the sampling variance of the GMR is inversely proportional to trial size (see Figure 1, left pane). At an infinite trial size, any GMR confidence interval will shrink down to zero and BE will be declared as long as the GMR is exactly between the 0.8 and 1.25 limits. IP extends standard power calculations to consider both the effect of fundamental uncertainty on GMRs and sampling uncertainty linked to trial size (Figure 1, right pane). When the fundamental GMR uncertainty is small compared to sampling uncertainty, both power and IP give approximately the same results, IP being always lower. As for power, sampling uncertainty shrinks as trial size increases, but fundamental GMR uncertainty does not and at infinite trial sizes the asymptotic IP values depend only on it. Since IP is a weighted average of power it does not necessarily reach 100% at infinite trial sizes. In that case, if the mean GMR is exactly at a BE limit, and if the distribution of fundamental uncertainty is symmetrical (*e.g.*, normal), the probability of declaring BE will be 50%; if the mean GMR is within the BE limits, the probability will be higher than 50%, if it is outside the BE limits it will be smaller. In fact, the distribution of the GMR at infinite trial size behaves exactly like the Bayesian GMR posterior distribution considered in the BEST test [17] or in [1]. Subsequently, the asymptotic IP can be used to decide on BE and an equivalent decision rule to TOST is to declare BE if the probability that GMR fall between the 0.8 or 1.25 limits is 90% or more.

Figure 1: Left pane: behavior of TOST power; as trial size increases, GMR confidence intervals shrink and BE acceptance become entirely determined by the position of GMR, assumed to be exactly known (A passing BE, B not passing BE). The vertical dashed lines indicate the absolute BE limits. Right pane: behavior of integrated power; test to reference difference has fundamental uncertainty; power is evaluated at infinitely many (here only 3 for display) GMR values distributed according to that uncertainty. In each case, GMR confidence intervals shrink as trial size increases and the decision on BE becomes always yes below the upper (rightmost) BE limit and no above it; the probability of passing BE is then equal the area under the green curve at the right of the upper BE limit. Densities are scaled arbitrarily for display clarity.

Methods

Workflow

We followed the workflow shown in Figure 2. The LAI-PBPK model development was performed previously [1–3], so the focus was on the meta-model development and subsequent VBE analyses. The meta-model development included meta-model fitting (using the simulated data from the PBPK model) and meta-model validation. For the VBE analyses, we used two calculation approaches : a frequentist framework (for IP and integrated safe-space) and a Bayesian framework (for posterior simulations and VBE assessment), as discussed in [1].

Figure 2: Workflow followed for LAI-PBPK model development, meta-model development and VBE analyses.

LAI PBPK model

A detailed description of the simulator’s LAI suspension model can be found in [2]. Briefly, the model can simulate the intra-muscular injection of a drug solid particle formulation at four concurrent sites. At each injection site, a spherical depot is formed. With time, solid drug particles undergo diffusion-layer-limited surface dissolution. This dissolution process is influenced by the physico-chemical properties of the drug and leads to the transfer of dissolved drug into the interstitial fluid sub-compartment of the depot. From there, the drug can diffuse to and from muscle cells and into the surrounding tissue where injection triggers an inflammatory immune response. As a result, immune cells (macrophages) gather around the depot and act as a physical barrier for drug diffusion. After traversing the Immune Cell Layer (ICL), the drug can reach the systemic circulation. From there, it can be transported by blood flow to the rest of the body where its distribution and elimination is described by any one of the PBPK models available in the simulator.

PP is rapidly converted in the body into paliperidone. In the model, the first-order metabolic conversion of prodrug to drug occurs within the interstitial fluid, ICL and systemic circulation with the same conversion rate constant, k_c . For PP we used a minimal PBPK model with metabolic conversion to paliperidone as the only clearance mechanism. For paliperidone, we used Simcyp’s full body PBPK model with first-order elimination. The model parameter values and validation details have been previously published [2].

Meta-model development

A meta-model for VBE assessment should be able to predict the GMRs and population variances of virtual trials given a trial size and the CQA values of the base PBBM model. In our case, it should predict the C_{max} GMR and variance for parallel BE trials of PP LAI suspension formulations, given the drug mean particle radius for test and reference. The model development steps were: 1) simulate C_{max} GMRs and population variances for large groups of subjects receiving different PP mean particle radii; 2) fit a fast-to-compute statistical model linking the C_{max} GMRs and population variances obtained to particle radius.

Our simulation strategy was guided by the original objective for our statistical model: the identification of CQA values leading to GMRs of 0.8 and 1.25 for type 1 error calculation. We first simulated 100,000 subjects receiving the reference formulation (with a radius of 4.6357 μm) and computed the group C_{max} geometric mean and its variance in log-space. Simulated analytical measurement random errors were added to the model predictions to adequately simulate data, as in [2]. We then changed the drug particle radius and simulated other groups of subjects receiving hypothetical test formulations. We started with 2500 subjects per test group and increased group size as we got closer to the solutions in order to have good precision in our search for the points at which GMR would be equal to 0.8 and 1.25. While this approach was well-suited to acquiring those values for type 1 error estimation, in a case where only a meta-model would be sought, group sample sizes could be adjusted to obtain a prescribed precision on the regression parameter estimates. For each altered radius value, we calculated a group C_{max} geometric mean and C_{max} variance in log-space, and a test over reference GMR. Regression coefficients were estimated by weighted least-squares (WLS) minimization, using the inverse GMR variances in log-space as weights for the GMR regression and group sizes as weights for the $\log(C_{max})$ variance regression.

Once defined and validated (see below), the meta-model could simulate the C_{max} GMR and the variance of $\log(C_{max})$ of PP LAI suspension formulation trials of any size, providing the inputs required to perform a TOST test. The final meta-model computed the average GMR as:

$$GMR_m = a_{GMR} \times \log(R) + b_{GMR} \quad (1)$$

where R is the test particle radius, a_{GMR} is the slope of the GMR vs. R relationship and b_{GMR} its intercept. The meta-model regression coefficients were estimated with some uncertainty, measured by their standard error (SE). This was modeled by sampling randomly a_{GMR} and b_{GMR} from normal distributions:

$$a_{GMR} \sim N(\mu_{a,GMR}, \sigma_{a,GMR}) \quad (2)$$

$$b_{GMR} \sim N(\mu_{b,GMR}, \sigma_{b,GMR}) \quad (3)$$

where $\mu_{a,GMR}$ is the WLS best estimate of a_{GMR} , $\sigma_{a,GMR}$ is its SE, and $\mu_{b,GMR}$ is the best estimate of b_{GMR} , $\sigma_{b,GMR}$ being its SE. For TOST test calculations, the variance of $C_{max} \log(\text{GMR})$ is also needed. That variance is the sum of the population variance for the test arm, scaled by number of subjects in the test arm, and a similar term for the reference group. The corresponding calculations by final meta-model computed are:

$$\sigma_{GMR}^2 = \frac{\exp(a_{\sigma,ref} \times R + b_{\sigma,ref})}{N_{ref}} + \frac{\exp(a_{\sigma,test} \times R + b_{\sigma,test})}{N_{test}} \quad (4)$$

where $a_{\sigma,ref}$ is the slope of the $\log(C_{max})$ variance vs. R relationship and $b_{\sigma,ref}$ its intercept. Here also, we had uncertainty in the regression coefficients, so we randomly sampled the slope and intercept from normal distributions:

$$a_{\sigma,i} \sim N(\mu_{a,\sigma}, \sigma_{a,\sigma}), \text{ with } i \in \{ref, test\} \quad (5)$$

$$b_{\sigma,i} \sim N(\mu_{b,\sigma}, \sigma_{b,\sigma}), \text{ with } i \in \{ref, test\} \quad (6)$$

where $\mu_{a,\sigma}$ is the WLS best estimate of a_{σ} , $\sigma_{a,\sigma}$ is its SE, and $\mu_{b,\sigma}$ is the best estimate of b_{σ} , $\sigma_{b,\sigma}$ being its SE.

Different trials should lead to different GMRs, because of inter-subject variability, measurement uncertainty *etc.* So, for each simulated trial a particular GMR was obtained using:

$$GMR \sim N(GMR_m, \sqrt{\sigma_{GMR}^2}) \quad (7)$$

TOST tests results were then computed in the standard way using GMR and σ_{GMR}^2 [18].

Meta-model validation

The fit of several candidate meta-models to the GMR and $\log(C_{max})$ variance data was evaluated visually and using the mean difference between data and predictions to select the best fitting model. To validate the final meta-model we first used it to perform Monte Carlo estimations TOST power as a function of trial size and test formulation mean particle radius and compared them with the estimates obtained with the full LAI-PBPK model [2]. We had found that power calculations are very sensitive to model parameterization and structure (see

discussion in [2,3]), meaning they should therefore be good tests for VBE models or surrogate meta-models.

An even more stringent test is to compute the probability of declaring BE at the limits of absolute CQA safe-space, where it should be at 5% if all the assumptions of the TOST test are fulfilled. We computed that probability as above with the meta-model by setting the test formulation mean particle radius at 6.82 μm . This is the upper limit of the true bioequivalence region, and was shown with the LAI-PBPK model to yield 5% probability of declaring BE. We also computed the probability of declaring BE as a function of test mean particle radius and trial size up to extremely large trial sizes (1 billion subject per arm), to understand the behavior of the meta-model as trial size approaches infinity. For those calculations, 10,000 trials were simulated at each radius size and trial size.

Integrated power calculations

Integrating power calculations over a one- or multi-dimensional distribution is computationally intensive, making it very challenging and time consuming when using a PBPK model. A validated meta-model can however speed up the required calculations.

As defined in O'Hagan *et al.* [4], the assurance, γ , of an event X (*e.g.*, passing BE with a TOST test) is the expected power of a test of it, where the expectation is taken with respect to the probability distribution $P(\boldsymbol{\theta})$, of the set $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ of parameters determining X (in our case, CQAs determining bioequivalence):

$$\gamma = E(\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})) = \int \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) P(\boldsymbol{\theta}) d\boldsymbol{\theta} \quad (8)$$

where π is the power function considered (here TOST power). The expectation, as usual, is the convolution integral of $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ and $P(\boldsymbol{\theta})$; hence the term of IP also used to designate statistical assurance. We computed γ by Monte Carlo sampling of 5000 values of the test formulation mean particle radius from lognormal distributions with specified mean (R) and SD (σ_R), reflecting various degrees of uncertainty on that CQA value. For each radius value sampled, the GMRs and population variances of 500 trials with n subjects per arm were then simulated using the meta-model. They were input to TOST tests and test results (yes/no) were used to compute the probability (as frequency over the 500 trials) of declaring BE (*i.e.*, IP). This was repeated for a geometric series of 60 arm sizes n ranging from 2 to 100,000 subjects. Those Monte-Carlo calculated estimates can be compared to asymptotic value (at infinite trial size) of IP, γ , calculated using an analytical formula adapted from Eq. 7 of O'Hagan *et al.* [4]:

$$\gamma = \Phi\left(\frac{\delta^i - \tau Z_{\alpha/2} - m}{\sqrt{\tau^2 + \nu}}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{-\delta^i + \tau Z_{\alpha/2} - m}{\sqrt{\tau^2 + \nu}}\right) \quad (9)$$

where δ^* is a clinically meaningful treatment difference, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the upper $100 \cdot \alpha\%$ significance point of the standard normal distribution, m is the mean of the *a priori* expected difference between treatment effects, ν is the variance of the uncertainty about that difference, and

$$\tau = \sqrt{\sigma_1^2/n_1 + \sigma_2^2/n_2} = \sqrt{(\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2)/n} \text{ if } n_1 = n_2 = n. \quad (10)$$

where σ_1 and σ_2 are the population variance of the effect in the test and reference groups, respectively, and n_1 and n_2 the respective arm sizes.

This must be adapted to the facts that TOST operates on the log-scale and that we use a meta-model: In the limit $n \rightarrow \infty, \tau \rightarrow 0$, so that:

$$\gamma = \Phi\left(\frac{\log(1.25) - G(R)}{v_b}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{\log(0.8) - G(R)}{v_a}\right) \quad (11)$$

where Φ is the normal cumulative distribution function (the Student-*t* distribution should be used in principle, but it is equivalent to the normal when $n \rightarrow \infty$), 0.8 and 1.25 are the usual BE limits, R is the mean particle radius of the test formulation studied, standard deviations v_a and v_b are given by:

$$v_a = \left| G\left(e^{[\log(R) - \sigma_R]}\right) - G(R) \right| \quad (12)$$

$$v_b = \left| G\left(e^{[\log(R) + \sigma_R]}\right) - G(R) \right| \quad (13)$$

where function $G(R)$ represent the part of the meta-model which computes $\log(\text{GMR})$ as a function of mean particle radius R . The latest two equations are approximations, because in fact the meta-model is slightly nonlinear over the range of mean drug particle radii investigated.

Integrated CQA safe-space calculations

We have previously identified and published the absolute safe space for mean drug particle radius (the product CQA) of the 3-month PP LAI suspension formulations, overlaid it with a map of the probability of passing BE (power for a given trial size, 200 subjects per arm in that case) [3]. Here, we replaced those power values by the corresponding asymptotic IP values.

Those were obtained by simulating 500 trials of 100,000 subjects per arm, for 5000 CQA (mean particle radius) randomly sampled from lognormal distributions centered at 100 log-mean particle radius values (to get a visually continuous curve) with a series of uncertainties specified by log-space SDs with values 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 or 0.20, corresponding to CVs of approximately that many percents.

Bayesian VBE assessment

Bayesian assessment of bioequivalence is based on evaluating the probability that C_{max} (and AUC , etc.) population test over reference GMR are within the [0.8, 1.25] limits [17]. This probability can be obtained by sampling random GMR values from their posterior distribution. In our case, those Bayesian calculations involved sampling 10,000 values of the test formulation mean particle radius from lognormal distributions 1) with means in log-space equal to the logarithm of the reference mean particle radius (4.6357 μm), or 2) test formulation mean particle radius equal to 5.500 μm . We used a series of SDs in log-space with values of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5. to reflect various degrees of uncertainty on the CQA value. For each test radius value sampled, the GMR mean was simulated with the meta-model (Eq. 7).

A shortcut can be taken because the mapping provided by our models between the GMR safe-space and the CQA safe-space is such that a point in the CQA safe-space necessarily leads to a point in the GMR safe-space. Such a mapping preserves probabilities (according to the Federer-Morse theorem [19]) and the probability for a test formulation to be in the GMR BE limits is equal to the probability for its CQAs to be within their *absolute* safe-space. In our case, mean particle radius safe-space is unidimensional and we know its bounds, A and B , from [3], so if we specify a probability distribution φ for mean particle radius R of a test formulation, the probability that it is BE can be directly obtained as:

$$P_{BE} = \int_A^B \varphi(R) dR \quad (14)$$

Software and hardware

All simulations of the LAI suspension model for meta-model development were performed with the *Simcyp*[®] *Simulator*, version 23, release 2. Those simulations were performed on Microsoft[®] Azure cloud virtual machines (with 26-core Intel[®] Xeon[®] Platinum 8272CL processors clocked at 2700 MHz base frequency). On such machines, 2500 subjects receiving

an LAI suspension injection of PP and followed up for 65 weeks are simulated in about 1 hr. Further statistical analyses and graphics were performed in *R* version 4.4.2 [20] on desktop computers (Lenovo ThinkPad T14s Gen 2i, with four-core Intel® Core™ i7-1165G7 11th generation processors clocked at 2803 MHz). Essential *R* scripts are given in Supplemental material.

Results

Meta-model development and validation

Plots for several regression models of GMR on mean particle radius are given in [3] and can be seen in the Supplemental material to this publication. Figure 3 shows the relationships obtained using various transformations of test formulation particle radii and $\log(C_{max})$ variance. The best-fitting model was a linear relationship between the drug particle radius and the logarithm of $\log(C_{max})$ variance (a double logarithm). Table 1 shows the values of the regression coefficients obtained; as for GMR regression, they are quite precise

Figure 3: Relationships between various transformations of particle radius and $\log(C_{max})$ variance. $\log(C_{max})$ variances were obtained by Monte Carlo simulations of large groups of subjects receiving a formulation with a radius given on the x-axis. The points' surface areas are proportional to the number of subjects simulated in each group. The *R* measure of fit is the average deviation between simulated $\log(C_{max})$ variances and regression-predicted $\log(C_{max})$.

Table 1: Values of the coefficients of the linear regression of the logarithm of $\log(C_{max})$ on the formulation drug particle radius.

Coefficient	Best estimate	Standard error	% Standard error
Intercept	-1.5385	0.00938	0.61%
Slope	0.16472	0.00173	1.05%

Figure 4 overlays 3-month PP LAI parallel trial power estimates computed using the meta-model with those computed using the full LAI-PBPK model. The two models give practically identical estimates, up to Monte Carlo sampling error. Yet, the meta-model runs 30,000 times faster than the PBPK model.

Figure 4: Comparison of the meta-model-based (in color) and PBPK model-based (in grey, [2]) power estimates as a function of trial size for parallel bioequivalence trials of test PP LAI suspension formulations with various mean initial particle radii (in μm). One thousand trials were simulated for each radius with the meta-model. The fluctuations in power values are due to Monte Carlo sampling randomness.

Figure 5 shows, however, that at the limits of safe-space and for extremely trial sizes, the meta-model does not behave exactly as expected. At the upper BE limit ($6.82 \mu\text{m}$, left panel of the Figure), the probability of bioequivalence (in fact, type 1 error) does not flatten out at 5% like it does with the original LAI-PBPK model [3], but keeps increasing. This is also seen happening along the vertical dotted line in the right panel of Figure 5, which shows that at the

high end of trial size the probability of declaring BE will stabilize at 50%. We have already observed that type 1 error calculations are very sensitive to small numerical errors [3]. Note also that at very large trial sizes the GME variance vanishes, and the TOST test has undefined behavior. The meta-model does have a small prediction uncertainty which will not vanish, however, and it is logical that this residual uncertainty leads to a 50% chance of declaring BE as trial size goes to infinity. Therefore, the meta-model does not seem adapted to precise calculations of very small probabilities for extremely large and unrealistic trial sizes. Keeping this in mind, we will still use the meta-model for further calculations.

Figure 5: Left pane: meta-model-based type 1 error estimate at the 0.8 BE limit (corresponding to a test formulation with mean particle radius 6.82 μm) as a function of trial size for PP LAI suspension formulations; the fluctuations of the grey line values are due to Monte Carlo sampling randomness; the red line is a smoothed version; the PBPK model-based estimates are consistently at 5%, see [3]. Right pane: probability of declaring BE estimates as a function of the test formulation mean particle radius, and for different parallel bioequivalence trial sizes; ten thousand trials were simulated for each radius with the meta-model.

Integrated power calculations

Figure 6 shows plots of IP as a function of the number of subjects per arm in BE or VBE trials. Trial sizes reach very high numbers because we were interested in the asymptotic behavior of IP. At the difference with standard power values that eventually reach value 1, except at the boundaries of absolute safe-space where there are uniformly 0.05 and go to zero beyond those boundaries [3], IP reaches different plateaus, depending on the location and spread of the distribution of expected CQA differences between test and reference. This is

because, as trial size increases, the uncertainty stemming from limited trial size vanishes (it is an inverse function of trial size, see Eq. 10), but the fundamental uncertainty about CQA differences does stay. The plateau values are important: they correspond to the probability that the CQA differences between test and reference lead to GMR values *within* the [0.8, 1.25] BE limits. We probably want this probability to be high and regulated. Eq. 11 gives an approximation of those plateau values (plotted as cross-hair points in Figure 6. That approximation assumes perfect lognormality and linearity and this approximation is quite exact when the test and reference ratios are expected, on average to be equal, but less precise if they are expected to differ on average. Note also that the meta-model has its own imprecision.

Figure 6: Meta-model-calculated IP (probability of declaring bioequivalence) as a function of trial size for parallel VBE trials of a perfectly bioequivalent test PP LAI suspension formulations (left panel, where mean particle radii for test and reference equal $4.6357 \mu\text{m}$), and for a test formulation mean initial particle radius of $5.5 \mu\text{m}$ (right panel). Uncertainty (SD in log-space) on radius was set at values of 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 (color-coded from yellow to red). The cross-hair points give the asymptotic value (at infinite trial size) of IP calculated using analytical formula 11.

CQA safe-space calculations with IP

Figure 7 displays various estimates of safe-space for INVEGA TRINZA[®]-like formulations' mean particle radius. The absolute safe-space limits have previously been found to be 2.77 and $6.82 \mu\text{m}$ for (shown by the boundaries of the crosshatched regions); inside those boundaries, the test formulation is truly BE [3]. The actual safe-space according to standard

power calculations is much narrower than this absolute safe-space (unless trial size is infinite): the probability of declaring BE become acceptable for a producer (*i.e.*, 80% or more) only between 4.24 and 5.03 μm for trials using 200 subjects per arm [3]. Beyond that, such trials would have low probability of declaring bioequivalence.

IP behaves quite differently from standard power estimates. Figure 7 displays the asymptotic (at infinite trial size) IP values when the distribution of test values for mean particle radius is centered on the reference value, but for different uncertainties (SD in log-space) on that difference. With the meta-model, that Figure took 10 minutes to compute. As mentioned in the “Background on integrated power (statistical assurance)” section above, asymptotic IP values higher than 90% can be used to decide on BE. The ranges within which that is true clearly depends on the underlying difference uncertainty; they are always narrower than the absolute safe-space (unless there were no uncertainty about the test to reference difference, which is unrealistic); they are also larger in our case than the range afforded by simply considering TOST power for trials with 200 subjects per arm (Table 2), but they shrink down as uncertainty increases. If uncertainty were to become too high, they would never reach the 90% threshold and safe-space would be null. As mentioned also in the “Background on integrated power (statistical assurance)” section above, asymptotic IP at the absolute safe-space limits is close to 50% (and clearly insufficient).

Figure 7: Safe space for the drug particle mean radius of PP LAI suspension formulations aiming to be bioequivalent to INVEGA TRINZA[®]. In the crosshatched region, the true test over reference GMR values are outside the [0.8,1.25] range. The purple lines correspond to the IP to declare BE for various values of uncertainty (SD in log-space, given in right margin) affecting the true test value of mean particle radius (assumed to be equal to the reference value). The grey solid line gives the usual statistical power of BE trials with 200 subjects per arm. The dotted horizontal lines mark probabilities 5% and 90%.

Table 2: Safe-space bounds according to asymptotic IP or standard power calculations.

logSD	Calculation mode	Lower bound	Upper bound
0*	Power or IP	2.77	6.82
0.05	IP	3.01	6.25
0.1	IP	3.28	5.88
0.15	IP	3.40	5.60
0.2	IP	3.60	5.22
0 [†]	Power	4.24	5.03

* Absolute safe-space bounds based on IP with no uncertainty (or power) at infinite size.

[†] Bounds based on having at least 80% power with trials of 200 subjects per arm [3].

Bayesian VBE assessment

Figure 8 shows meta-model-based estimates of the Bayesian posterior probability of declaring BE for a perfectly bioequivalent test formulation, where mean particle radii for the test and reference were equal to $4.6357 \mu\text{m}$, and for a test formulation where the mean particle radius was equal to $5.500 \mu\text{m}$ (not perfectly bioequivalent). As uncertainty increases, the probability of declaring BE decreases. For the test formulations with mean particle radius of $4.6357 \mu\text{m}$, the probability of declaring BE is larger than 90% for the first two SD values of particle radius in log-space (*i.e.*, 0.1 and 0.2 which give probabilities of 100% and 96% respectively). As we move away from a perfectly bioequivalent test formulation to a test formulation with mean particle radius of $5.500 \mu\text{m}$, only the SD value equal to 0.1 in log-space leads to a probability of declaring BE that is larger than 90% (specifically 98%).

Table 3 compares various estimates of the probability of declaring BE for various levels of uncertainty about the test formulation mean particle radius. Estimates were obtained using either the Bayesian posterior on GMR space, the Bayesian posterior on CQA space provided by Eq. 14, the asymptotic IP, or the approximate analytical formula for asymptotic IP (Eq. 11). The first three estimates closely agree and the last approximation deviates only a little from them.

Figure 8: Density histograms (in grey) and corresponding fitted normal density curves (in black) of posterior GMR (x-axis) distributions for five values SD of particle radius in log-space for a test formulation mean particle radius of $4.6357 \mu\text{m}$ (left five plots), and a radius of $5.5 \mu\text{m}$ (right five plots). In the crosshatched region, the GMR values are outside the $[0.8, 1.25]$ range. The Bayesian posterior probability of declaring BE (“P BE post”) and the asymptotic IP estimate (“P BE IP”) are given in each case.

Table 3: Probability of declaring BE for various levels of test formulation mean particle radius (CQA) uncertainty, according to several estimation methods (see text).

CQA uncertainty		Bayesian on GMR	Bayesian on CQA	Asymptotic IP	Analytic asymptotic IP
Mean particle radius	Log SD				
4.6357 μm	0.1	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
~	0.2	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.97
~	0.3	0.86	0.86	0.85	0.84
~	0.4	0.73	0.73	0.72	0.71
~	0.5	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.61
5.5000 μm	0.1	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98
~	0.2	0.86	0.86	0.84	0.84
~	0.3	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.72
~	0.4	0.66	0.66	0.65	0.63
~	0.5	0.58	0.58	0.57	0.55

We do not present a GMR safe-space plot for the Bayes VBE assessment, as it would be practically identical to Figure 7, given the equivalence of Bayesian posterior BE probability and asymptotic IP.

Discussion

Meta-model

The development of the meta-model was quite easy because the relationship between mean particle radius, test over reference GMR, and population variance turned out to be quite simple. It required preliminary simulations of large BE trials for test formulations of different mean particle radius using the LAI-PBPK model. For that, a total of about 500,000 subjects were simulated [3], which took about 200 hours on virtual multicore machines. Those calculations were therefore quite heavy, but the meta-model obtained runs about a billion time faster than the original mechanistic model and allowed us to investigate decision concepts and tools otherwise out of reach. For example, it took the meta-model about 10 minutes to do the calculations for Figure 7; they would have taken 17,000 years with the original model.

The meta-model is therefore extremely fast and fit for purpose but has a very limited applicability domain. It should be used only to simulate two-arm parallel clinical trials of PP LAI suspensions closely related to INVEGA TRINZA[®] with mean particle radius values

ranging from about 1 to 10 μm . For example, beyond 34 μm it predicts negative GMR values, which are not realistic. However, this would be very far from the range of bioequivalent particle radius values (the absolute safe space was found to extend from 2.77 μm to 6.82 μm for the PP products investigated here [3]). Another limitation of the meta-model is that it does not provide very precise estimates of very small probabilities in the case of extremely large trial sizes; therefore, it is probably not adequate for type 1 error calculations. The reason for this limitation is the finite precision of the meta-model predictions of GMR and population variance. It would be worth investigating better meta-models, what kinds of meta-models (Gaussian processes [13], *etc.*) would be best adapted to simulating trials in the case of multi-dimensional CQAs, how to minimize the number of PBPK runs needed to achieve a prescribed meta-model precision, and issues of automatic model checking. An important extension would be for them to simulate cross-over trials, which are more informative, and at the same time faster but more complex to simulate.

Note finally that the meta-model gave us insight into the behavior of the LAI-PBPK model by showing clearly that test over reference GMR depend linearly on log mean particle radius, and that simulated log population variances depend linearly on mean particle radius. That insight is useful when trying to understand how bioequivalence depends on LAI suspension CQAs.

Integrated power

The main point of this article is that neglecting the inherent and fundamental uncertainty in differences between test and reference CQA values is a major oversight of the current VBE approaches. CQA differences between test and reference are measured or estimated in various ways and always affected by uncertainty. Yet, recently Saadeddine *et al.* [21] did not consider that uncertainty in their VBE assessment. Arguably, the difference between test and reference was apparently small and the probability of passing BE was very high, but will that always be the case? Even closer to us, our recent publication [1] did estimate this uncertainty (Figure 5 in [1]) and took it into account when performing a Bayesian BE test (Figure 8 in [1]) but did not consider it at all when performing power analyses or safe-space calculations (Figure 9 in [1]), so that the Bayesian estimates of safe-space we presented are in fact estimate of the absolute (maximum) safe space and not fully Bayesian. To be fair, even when planning a standard BE trial, that uncertainty should be considered, at least by taking a conservative over-estimate of expected PK metrics differences. Conservative estimates, however, are

arbitrary and it is much preferable to use the concept of statistical assurance (IP). In a nutshell, IP is more essential to consider than just standard power.

However, why even do an IP analysis in VBE assessment? We are not really interested in the size of virtual trials as they can be of any size at practically no cost and no pain to anyone. As discussed in [1], deciding on VBE on the basis of a virtual trial, or even a collection of them, only adds unneeded sampling uncertainty to the process and degrades the information available in the simulation model. This may be an “historical” option, like animal experiments in safety assessment, and is a further protection of consumers (at the expense of higher producer risk), but then it goes beyond the mandate of making sure that GMRs are with 90% probability within the regulatory BE limits, and we should remember that producer risk is indirectly also a consumer risk. At the same time, we currently disregard fundamental uncertainty about CQA differences. A better and logical approach is to compute IP which averages power over many trials, taking fundamental uncertainty into account, which is fair for consumers and producers alike, and at the same time use the asymptotic IP value which gives the best estimate of the probability that the test formulation CQAs will lead to acceptable PK metrics GMR. It turns out that asymptotic IP is equivalent to the logical Bayesian posterior decision rule [22], which is an interesting bridging result. Kruschke [22] also mentions passing integrated power, but does not make the connection with statistical assurance and his approach stays data-centric.

Note that beyond the requirements that the models used for VBE be sufficiently validated, the above also implies that a verifiable statistical distribution of differences between test and reference CQAs should be provided. We will further discuss this point later on.

Finally, we found that the theoretical approximation proposed in [4] and adapted to the meta-model (Eq. 11) matches reasonably the meta-model asymptotic calculations. This helps validating our calculations, its use would be limited because it does require anyway a meta-model for its construction, which in the absence of a meta-model would be very computationally expensive.

Safe-space

There can be several definitions of safe-space. They are all conditional on the definition of BE. We will restrict ourselves, as we have done so far, on average bioequivalence as defined by the US FDA [23]. In the most general definition of average BE, two products are bioequivalent if their population average C_{max} and AUC GMRs are within some prescribed

limits (*e.g.*, 0.8 and 1.25). Let's put aside the question of how to prove that the GMRs are within those limits and assume that we can estimate population average GMRs exactly and for any formulation we want. We could then try formulations with many different CQA values, and we would know whether or not they lead to GMRs with the [0.8, 1.25] limits. We could therefore establish which CQA values lead to bioequivalence and draw the limits of what we will call the *absolute* CQA safe-space for those formulation. Near the limits of that safe-space, GMR values would be very close to 0.8 or 1.25 but just above or below, respectively. CQA values should certainly not fall outside of absolute safe-space, because in that case BE would fail surely. In practice, with actual clinical trials, absolute CQA safe-space is impossible to obtain because trials do not give us exact population GMRs. However, if we have a mathematical or computer model we trust and that can accurately compute GMRs from CQAs, we can use it to find the absolute CQA safe-space by mathematical inversion, and up to any degree of accuracy desired. Computations can be heavy, but this is how we estimated (up to a reasonable level of accuracy) the absolute mean particle radius safe-spaces [3].

Yet, a real formulation could never be marketed if it were near the limits of its absolute safe-space, because safe-space is marred by uncertainties. It is useful to overlay absolute CQA safe-space with maps of the probability of declaring BE, like in Figure 7. A usual map (see for example [24]) is the standard power estimate (grey curve in Figure 7). Such a map is obtained for a given trial size and accounts for sampling variability (which directly affect the confidence intervals of the TOST test). When trial size is limited by the economic or ethical considerations (which apply only to real clinical trials), the feasible safe-space can be quite small, like in our case. However, as discussed above, a serious problem is that standard power calculations neglect the effect of our fundamental uncertainty about CQA differences, which is present both data-based and in model-based BE assessments. The necessary fix can be brought about by IP maps, which for a given trial size are even more restrictive of safe-space. But, as already discussed, in the case of model-based BE assessment, there is not valid reason to limit virtual trial size for either standard power or IP calculations (except the desire to mimic reality by convention, however dire reality is). IP maps should therefore be replaced by asymptotic IP-maps (the purple lines in in Figure 7) obtained at infinite (at least very large) trial size. In our case, the extent of safe-space according to asymptotic IP is intermediate between standard power-based safe-space and absolute safe-space and depends on fundamental uncertainty. Given the correspondence between asymptotic IP and Bayesian posterior BE tests, direct decision-making is possible with asymptotic IP maps: if asymptotic

IP does not reach 90%, safe-space is null, and the test product cannot be declared bioequivalent.

Here also we have a shorter way to compute the probability of BE (through Eq. 14), and the formula, this time, is exact.

Bayesian VBE assessment

Our Bayesian calculations are similar to the “Bayesian Estimation (BEST)” procedure [17,22], adapted to model-based BE assessment. BEST takes in input data from a BE trial and estimates the posterior distribution of the PK metrics GMR; when the lower and upper bounds of the posterior 90% credibility interval of the log-transformed GMR (containing the 90% most likely values for the true GMR) fall between $\log(0.80)$ and $\log(1.25)$, BEST supports BE. This is equivalent to requiring that both posterior probabilities that GMR is below 0.8 or above 1.25 do not exceed 5%, as use here and in [1]. For model-based assessment, the posterior GMR distribution should be obtained from integration of *in vitro* and eventually clinical data from a validation trial [1]. Here, since we are simply simulating model parameters from given distributions, Monte Carlo simulations are used to obtain samples of values for GMR, and the concept is the same. In the BEST procedure, GMR posterior distributions are obviously directly affected by the size of the clinical trial on which inference is based. In a model-based assessment, the strength of the *in vitro* evidence, and the size of the validation trial would affect the GMR posterior in the same way.

The major problem we met came from the fact that the LAI-PBPK model needed to integrate *in vitro* data in VBE takes much longer to compute than the distributional models used in BEST [17]. In this case, computing and integrating the posterior probability distribution of GMRs to obtain the probability of BE is almost impossible and the availability of a meta-model is essential for the feasibility of this approach. Note, however, that if the boundaries of the CQA safe-space are easy to compute, Eq. 14 can be used to estimate the probability of BE by Monte Carlo integration, without using even a meta-model. We showed how to perform those calculations and that they are equivalent to calculations of asymptotic IP. Those are major new results for making best use of all information available in VBE assessments, without obfuscating them with clinical trial simulations and TOST testing.

Conclusion

We have found that meta-models are extremely powerful tools for VBE modeling and assessment. There is an avenue of research to be devoted to them in this field, and in PBPK modeling in general. They even offer such insights in VBE that they indicate ways to dispense with them by allowing the validation or at least the critical evaluation of analytical shortcuts (*e.g.*, our Eqs 11 and 14).

The notion of statistical assurance (integrated power, IP) was found to be fundamental in VBE assessment. A proper accounting of uncertainties in VBE must include CQA differences between test and reference formulations, as it is one of its two main components, on par with model quality. As for standard power, issues of “virtual trial” size in VBE are a mind trap and have no real meaning nor import; they obfuscate the evidence available and should be bypassed by focusing on PI behavior in the large sample limit, where it does not degenerate (at the difference of standard power). We showed that asymptotic IP calculations bridge power calculations and Bayesian BE assessment and that asymptotic IP above 0.9 are a valid BE decision rule, equivalent to the well-known Bayesian (BEST) rule [17]. Using such a rule would be principled and coherent with the current BE regulations. It would require generic drug sponsors to justify to the fullest extent the uncertainty (alternatively, precision) of the difference they expect between their product and the reference formulation.

As to CQA safe space, understanding its maximum extent (absolute safe-space) is fundamental in VBE. It conditions the estimation of type 1 error [3] and is the background over which operational estimates of risk (*e.g.*, asymptotic IP) can be represented. We show that with asymptotic IP or, equivalently Bayesian posterior estimates, BE acceptance can be directly determined from such plots.

Bayesian posterior estimates of the probability of BE are well established and this work demonstrate their natural applicability to model-based VBE. They are also quite natural and simple to compute, being based on probability calculus, rather than on statistical concepts like power.

We explored in detail VBE assessment steps following model validation and introduced therein the concept of meta-models. Our demonstration falls short, however, of showing how to integrate evidence brought about by *in vitro* data or by a validation clinical trial and transform it into a distribution of CQA values to overlay on safe-space. Those steps have been

so far illustrated separately [1,24]. More work is needed to fully organize and refine the workflow steps of VBE analyses, and this is the scope of our on-going work.

References

1. Bois FY, Brochot C. A Bayesian framework for virtual comparative trials and bioequivalence assessments. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2024;15:1404619.
2. Bois FY *et al*. Virtual bioequivalence assessment of long-acting injectable suspensions using PBPK modeling: part 1. Impact of particle size on formulation variability. submitted;
3. Bois FY *et al*. Virtual bioequivalence of long-acting injectable suspensions using using PBPK modeling: Part 2. Type 1 error and safe-space analyses. submitted;
4. O'Hagan A, Stevens JW, Campbell MJ. Assurance in clinical trial design. *Pharmaceutical Statistics*. 2005;4:187–201.
5. Chen D-G (Din), Ho S. From statistical power to statistical assurance: it's time for a paradigm change in clinical trial design. *Communications in Statistics - Simulation and Computation*. 2017;46:7957–71.
6. Chen D-G, Fraser MW, Cuddeback GS. Assurance in intervention research: a bayesian perspective on statistical power. *Journal of the Society for Social Work and Research*. 2018;9:159–73.
7. Ring A, Lang B, Kazaroho C, Labes D, Schall R, Schütz H. Sample size determination in bioequivalence studies using statistical assurance. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 2019;85:2369–77.
8. Kasim MF, Watson-Parris D, Deaconu L, Oliver S, Hatfield P, Froula DH, et al. Building high accuracy emulators for scientific simulations with deep neural architecture search. *Machine Learning: Science and Technology*. 2022;3:015013.
9. O'Hagan A. Curve fitting and optimal design for prediction. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*. 1978;40:1–24.
10. Welch WJ, Buck RobertJ, Sacks J, Wynn HP, Mitchell TJ, Morris MD. Screening, predicting, and computer experiments. *Technometrics*. 1992;34:15.
11. Sacks J, Welch WJ, Mitchell TJ, Wynn HP. Design and analysis of computer experiments (with discussion). *Statistical Science*. 1989;4:409–35.
12. Haylock RG, O'Hagan A. On inference for outputs of computationally expensive algorithms with uncertainty on the inputs. In: Bernardo JM, Berger JO, Dawid AP, Smith AFM, editors. *Bayesian Statistics 5* [Internet]. Oxford University PressOxford; 1996. p. 629–38. Available from: <https://academic.oup.com/book/54042/chapter/422210172>
13. Oakley JE, O'Hagan A. Probabilistic sensitivity analysis of complex models: a Bayesian approach. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*. 2004;66:751–69.
14. Jones DR. A taxonomy of global optimization methods based on response surfaces. *Journal of Global Optimization*. 2001;21:345–83.

15. Mohanty SP, Koungianos E. Polynomial metamodel based fast optimization of nano-CMOS oscillator circuits. *Analog Integrated Circuits and Signal Processing*. 2014;79:437–53.
16. Ranftl S, Von Der Linden W. Bayesian surrogate analysis and uncertainty propagation. *The 40th International Workshop on Bayesian Inference and Maximum Entropy Methods in Science and Engineering* [Internet]. MDPI; 2021. p. 6. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2673-9984/3/1/6>
17. Peck C, Campbell G, Yoo I, Feng K, Hu M, Zhao L. Comparing a Bayesian approach (BEST) with the two one-sided t-tests (TOSTs) for bioequivalence studies. *The AAPS Journal*. 2022;24:97.
18. Schuirmann DJ. A comparison of the two one-sided tests procedure and the power approach for assessing the equivalence of average bioavailability. *Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Biopharmaceutics*. 1987;15:657–80.
19. Federer H, Morse AP, Charmilou LA. Some properties of measurable functions. *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society*. 1943;49:270–7.
20. R Development Core Team. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, <http://www.R-project.org>) [Internet]. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing; 2013. Available from: <http://www.R-project.org>
21. Saadeddin A, Purohit V, Huh Y, Wong M, Maulny A, Dowty ME, et al. Virtual bioequivalence assessment of ritlecitinib capsules with incorporation of observed clinical variability using a physiologically based pharmacokinetic model. *The AAPS Journal*. 2024;26:17.
22. Kruschke JK. Bayesian estimation supersedes the t test. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*. 2013;142:573–603.
23. US FDA C for DE and R. *Statistical Approaches to Establishing Bioequivalence* [Internet]. US FDA; 2001 [cited 2024 Dec 21]. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/media/70958/download>
24. Hsieh N-H, Bois FY, Tsakalozou E, Ni Z, Yoon M, Sun W, et al. A Bayesian population physiologically based pharmacokinetic absorption modeling approach to support generic drug development: application to bupropion hydrochloride oral dosage forms. *Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics*. 2021;48:893-908 (PMC8604781).

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Material is provided.